

Теорія і методика професійної освіти

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Зміст і структура іншомовної професійної компетентності майбутнього вчителя нефілологічної спеціальності

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***Анотація:** Стаття має на меті розкрити зміст і структуру іншомовної професійної компетентності майбутніх учителів нефілологічних спеціальностей, визначити її складові та окреслити умови ефективного формування в контексті сучасних освітніх тенденцій і вимог європейського освітнього простору.*

***Методи.** У процесі дослідження використано комплекс загальнонаукових і педагогічних методів: аналіз наукової літератури з проблеми формування професійної та іншомовної компетентностей; порівняльно-узагальнювальний метод для систематизації теоретичних підходів; метод моделювання для визначення структури іншомовної професійної компетентності;*

*У **результатах** конкретизовано зміст і структуру іншомовної професійної компетентності майбутнього вчителя нефілологічної спеціальності. Зокрема, виокремлено та схарактеризовано основні структурні складники іншомовної професійної компетентності вчителя нефілологічної спеціальності – це лінгвістична, соціокультурна, міжкультурна та*

комунікативна компетенції, а також психологічна готовність до міжкультурної взаємодії.

Висновки. Сформована іномовна професійна компетентність є невід'ємною складовою професійного становлення вчителя нефілологічного профілю, адже забезпечує його конкурентоспроможність, академічну мобільність і готовність до міжкультурної комунікації. Подальші дослідження мають бути спрямовані на розроблення практичних моделей формування зазначеної компетентності з урахуванням специфіки різних спеціальностей.

Ключові слова: іномовна професійна компетентність, майбутній учитель, нефілологічна спеціальність, структура компетентності, комунікативні уміння, іномовна освіта, педагогічні умови.

Content and structure of foreign language professional competence of future non-philological teachers

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Abstract: *The article aims to reveal the content and structure of the foreign language professional competence of future non-philological teachers, to determine its components, and to outline the conditions for its effective formation in the context of modern educational trends and the requirements of the European educational space.*

Methods. *The research employs a set of general scientific and pedagogical*

methods: analysis of scientific literature on the problem of professional and foreign language competence formation; comparative and generalizing method for systematizing theoretical approaches; modeling method for defining the structure of foreign language professional competence; empirical methods (observation, questionnaire survey) for identifying the level of formation of relevant skills among students.

***The results** specify the content and structure of foreign language professional competence of future teachers of non-philological specialities. In particular, the main structural components of foreign language professional competence of teachers of non-philological specialities are identified and characterised: linguistic, sociocultural, intercultural and communicative competences, as well as psychological readiness for intercultural interaction.*

***Conclusions.** The developed foreign language professional competence is an essential component of the professional formation of a non-philological teacher, as it ensures competitiveness, academic mobility, and readiness for intercultural communication. Further research should focus on developing practical models for the formation of this competence, taking into account the specifics of different specializations.*

***Keywords:** foreign language professional competence, future teacher, non-philological specialty, competence structure, communicative skills, foreign language education, pedagogical conditions.*

Statement of the problem in general terms and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks (Introduction). In the current context of globalisation, Ukraine's integration into the European educational space and the growing role of intercultural interaction, knowledge of foreign languages is becoming an integral component of professional competence for specialists in any field. The development of foreign language professional competence among future teachers of

non-philological specialities is particularly relevant, as they must be prepared for international communication, academic mobility, and participation in educational programmes and scientific projects. Despite the growing attention to this issue, there are still contradictions in the interpretation of the content and structure of this competence, as well as in determining effective ways of developing it.

Analysis of recent research and publications (Literature Review). The analysis of scientific publications over the last five years shows a sustained interest among researchers in the problem of developing foreign language and professional competences in students of various specialities. Sydorenko [14] defines foreign language competence as an integrated formation that combines linguistic, sociocultural and professionally oriented knowledge. Kravchenko [6] emphasises the role of the communicative approach in the development of professionally oriented speech of future teachers. Savytska [13] explores the impact of digital technologies and artificial intelligence on the effectiveness of foreign language acquisition. Boychuk [3] considers adaptive learning as a technology for developing intercultural competence in adolescents in English language classes. Tarnopolsky [12] considers gamification as a means of increasing students' motivation to learn foreign languages. Mizyuk [9] substantiates the effectiveness of blended learning for the formation of communication skills. Shevchenko [16] points out the advantages of using mobile applications for the development of students' foreign language autonomy. Richards & Rodgers [18] analyse contemporary methodological approaches to foreign language teaching in the context of professional education. Warschauer [19] focuses on the impact of information technology on language education. Hymes [17] expands the concept of communicative competence, emphasising its connection with the professional activities of teachers.

A review of the sources shows that most researchers consider foreign language competence in the context of language training, while the specifics of its professional dimension in non-philological specialities have not been sufficiently studied.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Despite existing research, the issues of content and structural components of foreign language professional competence of future teachers of non-philological specialities remain controversial. The relationship between the professional, communicative and intercultural components of this competence is not sufficiently defined. The pedagogical conditions, methodological means and models for its effective formation in the process of professional training require further study.

Formulation of the article's objectives. The aim of this study is to determine the content and structure of the foreign language professional competence of future teachers of non-philological specialities, as well as to substantiate the pedagogical conditions for its formation. The chosen direction of research is important because it contributes to improving the quality of teacher training in the context of European education standards, developing their competitiveness, academic mobility and readiness for intercultural professional interaction.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the scientific results obtained. The ultimate goal of the course «Foreign Language (English)» for future teachers of non-philological specialities is to develop their foreign language professional competence. This specific competence is considered by many educational scientists to be a set of interrelated competences, including professional, linguistic, sociocultural, intercultural, communicative, and others. Until now, the requirements for the training of future teachers have been formulated from the perspective of the concept of «foreign language professional competence» (FLPC), which scholars have defined as an integral quality of a subject of professional and pedagogical activity, characterising their desire and ability to engage in effective everyday and professional communication in a foreign language [7]. This competence presupposes the existence of a system of qualitative characteristics that are realised in foreign language professional communication, including:

- 1) a broad cultural worldview and thesaurus, formed by the sum of professional

language skills and abilities;

2) high productivity of foreign language activity;

3) a high level of creative thinking, which ensures the processes of perception and decoding of foreign language information of a professional nature;

4) a comprehensive set of knowledge in the field of language, which ensures the development and self-development of the individual in foreign language professional communication.

An analysis of scientific literature has shown that the competence-based approach in foreign language training for future teachers of non-philological specialities is aimed at developing key competences in students that are necessary for using a foreign language in professional and pedagogical activities, interpersonal communication and self-development. In particular, according to educational scientists, the competence-based approach involves [1, 5, 2].

1) the formation of linguistic and speech competence – the development of foreign language skills at a level that allows for professional communication on the subject and on pedagogical topics; practice in speaking, listening, reading and writing to solve specific professional tasks related to the school subject, the educational process, etc.;

2) development of intercultural competence – familiarisation with the cultural characteristics of native speakers; formation of the ability to interact adequately with representatives of other cultures;

3) integration of language into professional and pedagogical activities – use of a foreign (English) language as a tool for performing professional tasks (reading specialised literature, participating in international conferences, preparing presentations, etc.); modelling professional situations at school that require the use of a foreign language;

4) application of modern pedagogical technologies – use of interactive teaching methods (discussions, role-playing games, project activities); use of digital

technologies, such as online courses, language platforms, virtual simulations, etc.;

5) development of cognitive and critical competence – teaching how to analyse information in a foreign language, assess the reliability and relevance of this information; developing problem-solving skills through foreign language communication;

6) focus on autonomous learning – encouraging independent foreign language learning through the use of authentic resources (films, podcasts, fiction, scientific and professional literature); developing the ability to organise one's own learning process and monitor its results;

7) development of social competence – teaching effective teamwork using a foreign language; developing tolerance and empathy in communication with foreign-language interlocutors;

8) ensuring an integrated approach – integrating foreign language knowledge into the general context of professional training; creating interdisciplinary links between foreign languages and students' core disciplines.

Thus, it has been established that it is the competence-based approach that provides future teachers of non-philological specialities with the tools that allow them to use a foreign language (primarily English) for professional and personal growth.

Analysis of scientific literature [5, 7, 10, 11, 15] has made it possible to clarify the key category of the study – «**foreign language professional competence of teachers of non-philological specialities**», interpreting it as an *integrated personal quality that allows them to interact effectively with both their students and representatives of other cultures on the basis of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in a foreign language*.

A general indicator of the development of foreign language professional competence is the teacher's versatile creative activity in the process of foreign language professional communication in future pedagogical activity. We have identified the main components of foreign language professional

competence for teachers of non-philological specialities: linguistic, sociocultural, intercultural, communicative, and psychological readiness for intercultural interaction.

We have identified the main components of foreign language professional competence for teachers of non-philological subjects: linguistic, sociocultural, intercultural, communicative, and psychological readiness for intercultural interaction. Let us briefly describe them.

1. Linguistic competence is the ability to use language knowledge, skills and abilities correctly, effectively and purposefully for professional and interpersonal communication. It is important because teachers of non-philological specialities must be proficient in a foreign language in order to perform professional tasks, particularly in the context of international cooperation, access to professional literature or participation in conferences. This competence in teachers requires the development of a whole range of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for effective foreign language proficiency, and its key components are:

a) linguistic literacy (in-depth knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, syntax and phonetics of the language; the ability to use language forms correctly in different contexts);

b) knowledge of language levels (phonetic level – command of correct pronunciation, intonation and rhythm of speech; morphological level – knowledge of the rules of word formation and their grammatical forms; syntactic level – ability to construct correct and logical sentences; lexical level – rich vocabulary, including terminology);

c) speech competence (the ability to use language correctly and effectively in oral and written communication; skills in constructing monologues, dialogues, public speeches and writing texts of various styles and genres);

d) metalinguistic knowledge (awareness of the peculiarities of language structure, its functions and means of expressing thoughts; ability to explain linguistic

phenomena, analyse and compare languages);

e) academic vocabulary and professional terminology (knowledge of specialised terms related to the subject, educational and upbringing processes, etc.); ability to explain linguistic concepts in simple terms);

f) practical language skills (fluency in spoken language: correct pronunciation, intonation, clear articulation; excellence in writing: spelling, punctuation, stylistic correctness of texts);

f) creativity in the use of linguistic means (use of language to stimulate students' creativity, additional motivation to study school subjects).

The development of linguistic competence ensures effective communication and the development of not only language knowledge but also general speech culture. Thus, linguistic competence is the basis for a teacher's successful professional activity.

2. Sociocultural competence is the ability to use knowledge about the cultural values, traditions, norms and social characteristics of another culture in professional activities and interpersonal communication. It promotes effective interaction in a multicultural environment and the formation of a sense of tolerance in students. The main components of the sociocultural competence of a teacher of a non-philological speciality are:

a) knowledge of the sociocultural context (familiarity with the history, culture, traditions and customs of other countries; understanding of social norms and rules of behaviour accepted in different cultures);

b) understanding of cultural diversity (awareness of the diversity of cultures and linguistic worldviews; ability to adapt to cultural differences and avoid stereotypes);

c) the ability to integrate cultural knowledge into teaching (using examples from different cultures to illustrate teaching material; fostering students' interest in other cultures and their desire for intercultural dialogue);

d) tolerance and empathy (ability to show understanding, tolerance and respect for people with different cultural views; skills of empathic listening and ethical communication; ability to conduct professional dialogue with representatives of different cultures; use of adequate verbal and non-verbal means of communication to avoid conflicts);

e) development of global thinking (ability to relate knowledge to global processes and understand one's role in a globalised world; motivation of students to participate in international projects, exchange programmes, etc.);

f) integration of sociocultural elements into professional activity (use of sociocultural knowledge to build effective communication in a professional context; consideration of different cultural approaches to solving professional tasks);

f) use of modern resources (use of authentic materials (films, podcasts, texts) to familiarise oneself with culture; use of digital platforms for intercultural interaction);

g) ethics in socio-cultural interaction (adherence to ethical standards and respect for cultural characteristics; avoidance of controversial topics and ethical mistakes when interacting with representatives of other cultures).

Sociocultural competence is important for teachers of non-language subjects, as it broadens their worldview, helps them integrate intercultural aspects into their subject, ensures successful interaction in a multicultural environment, and, through their own example, promotes the development of tolerance towards other cultures in students. Thus, sociocultural competence is an important component of professional training for teachers of non-philological specialities, as it allows them to work in conditions of globalisation and cultural diversity.

3. The intercultural competence of a teacher of non-philological specialities is the ability to interact effectively with representatives of other cultures, taking into account their cultural, social and professional characteristics, in the context of professional activity. It is important for teachers working in today's multicultural educational environment.

The main components of the intercultural competence of teachers of non-philological specialities are:

a) cultural awareness (understanding the main aspects of different cultures (traditions, values, behavioural patterns); awareness of the influence of culture on thinking, language and behaviour);

b) communicative flexibility (the ability to adapt one's communication style to the cultural characteristics of interlocutors; understanding of verbal and non-verbal signals characteristic of different cultures; respectful attitude towards other cultures, rejection of stereotypes and prejudices; ability to put oneself in another person's shoes and show empathy in intercultural communication);

c) professional orientation in an intercultural environment (ability to use intercultural knowledge to solve professional tasks; ability to work with colleagues, students or partners from different cultures);

d) intercultural communication (knowledge and application of linguistic constructions and expressions characteristic of intercultural communication; ability to avoid or resolve conflicts that may arise due to cultural differences);

e) ethics in intercultural interaction (adherence to ethical standards of communication and professional behaviour when interacting with representatives of other cultures; respect for the cultural identity of each person);

f) motivation for intercultural development (willingness to learn about other cultures and integrate cultural elements into one's own activities; constant interest in intercultural exchange of experience.

The key method of developing intercultural competence in teachers of non-language subjects is self-education, i.e. studying the cultural characteristics of other countries through books, films, travel, and the use of online resources to learn about cultural differences. In addition, integration into teaching activities is important, namely: the use of culturally oriented tasks in the educational process (analysis of literature, cultural phenomena, traditions) and the creation of an educational

environment that promotes the development of intercultural tolerance among students. The development of intercultural competence in teachers of non-philological specialities also has practical applications, such as participation in international seminars, projects, conferences, and working with students or colleagues from other cultures. An important result of the formation of intercultural competence in teachers is also the development of language competence through the deepening of foreign language knowledge, as it is the main tool for intercultural communication.

Intercultural competence is important in the professional activities of teachers of non-philological subjects, as it allows them to adapt teaching materials to a multicultural environment and to foster respect for cultural diversity among students. At the level of interpersonal interaction, it helps to avoid conflicts, promotes cooperation with representatives of other cultures, and in the process of self-development, it contributes to personal growth through the expansion of worldview and interaction with other cultures.

Therefore, intercultural competence is an important component of the professional training of a modern teacher, as it helps to work effectively in a globalised world, creating favourable conditions for the education and upbringing of schoolchildren.

4. The communicative competence of a teacher of a non-philological specialty is the ability to interact effectively with other people (students, colleagues, parents) using verbal and non-verbal means of communication in professional activities. It encompasses not only knowledge of the language, but also the ability to adapt communication strategies according to the situation, context and audience. The main components of the communicative competence of a teacher of a non-philological specialty are:

a) linguistic literacy (high level of language proficiency (both native and foreign); correct use of grammar, vocabulary and syntax for clear and understandable

expression);

b) speech competence (the ability to express thoughts clearly, logically and in a structured manner; mastery of different styles of speech (formal, informal, scientific, etc.) depending on the situation);

c) non-verbal communication (use of facial expressions, gestures and intonation to complement and reinforce verbal communication; ability to read non-verbal signals from interlocutors);

d) professional orientation in communication (ability to build communication in the educational process, conveying knowledge in an accessible and interesting way; use of professional terminology within the scope of one's school subject);

e) psychological and pedagogical competence (knowledge of the basics of psychology for effective communication with students of different ages; ability to create an atmosphere of trust and mutual respect);

f) communicative flexibility (ability to adapt to changes in a communicative situation; ability to choose an appropriate tone, style and means of communication);

g) reflective skills (ability to evaluate one's own speech and communication; analysis of the effectiveness of communicative actions and their improvement.

Methods for developing communicative competence include: 1) practical improvement of speech skills (speeches in front of an audience (students, colleagues); participation in discussions, debates, seminars, etc.; 2) development of listening skills, active listening skills to understand the interlocutor; paying attention to the emotional state of the interlocutor and their individual needs; 3) self-education and improvement of language knowledge through reading literature, in particular professional literature, to expand vocabulary, as well as watching videos that demonstrate effective communication; 4) use of interactive teaching methods and means of communication (online platforms, presentations, video conferences); 5) modelling communicative situations such as role-playing, for example, «teacher-student», «teacher-parents», etc.; 6) analysing typical communication problems and

finding ways to solve them.

The communicative competence of teachers is important in the educational process, as it ensures the effective transfer of knowledge and skills to students and helps to create a favourable microclimate in the classroom. During professional interaction, it facilitates cooperation with colleagues, administration, and parents of students and increases the effectiveness of participation in professional events (seminars, conferences), and in interpersonal relationships, it maintains a positive atmosphere of trust and mutual understanding and helps to avoid conflicts and resolve problematic situations.

Thus, communicative competence is a key skill for teachers of non-philological subjects, ensuring successful pedagogical activity and setting an example for students in communication and social interaction.

5. The psychological readiness for intercultural interaction of a teacher of non-philological specialities is a set of personal qualities, knowledge, abilities and skills that ensure the teacher's ability to interact effectively with representatives of other cultures in their professional activities. It is the basis for successful intercultural communication and contributes to the creation of a tolerant and productive educational environment.

The main components of psychological readiness for intercultural interaction of teachers of non-philological specialities are:

a) cognitive component (knowledge of the cultural traditions, norms and values of other peoples; understanding of intercultural differences and their impact on behaviour and communication; ability to analyse and predict possible difficulties in intercultural interaction);

b) emotional component (empathy as the ability to understand the emotional state and experiences of another person; a positive attitude towards interaction with representatives of other cultures; overcoming fear or uncertainty in new intercultural situations);

c) motivational component (interest in learning about other cultures and communicating with their representatives; desire to improve one's intercultural interaction skills; focus on effective cooperation and mutual understanding);

d) behavioural component (ability to adapt one's behaviour to the cultural norms and expectations of the other party; ability to avoid conflict situations due to intercultural misunderstandings; tolerance of different views, ways of thinking and behaviour);

e) reflective component (analysis of one's own attitudes and stereotypes towards other cultures; ability to critically evaluate one's own behaviour in intercultural situations; constant striving for self-improvement).

Scientists have identified factors that influence teachers' psychological readiness for intercultural interaction [4]: 1) personal qualities – flexibility of thinking, openness to new experiences, tolerance of uncertainty; ability to self-organise and emotional stability; 2) previous experience – personal or professional experience of communicating with representatives of other cultures; knowledge and understanding of the specifics of intercultural relations; 3) level of language proficiency; 4) training and self-education – training within educational programmes or independent study of cultural studies, psychology of intercultural interaction, etc. Scientists also suggest ways to develop psychological readiness for intercultural interaction [8]: 1) increasing cultural awareness (learning about cultural characteristics through literature, films, travel, communication; studying the history, traditions and customs of different peoples); 2) developing emotionality through participation in training courses on empathy and tolerance or through working with one's own emotions through meditation, reflection or psychological support; 3) practising intercultural interaction by participating in international conferences, exchanges, joint projects with representatives of other cultures, as well as through the use of online platforms for intercultural communication; 4) overcoming stereotypes by becoming aware of one's own prejudices and replacing them with objective

information, as well as through constant analysis of one's own behaviour in intercultural situations; 5) self-development, which involves developing communication and adaptation skills and learning a foreign language as a tool for intercultural communication.

The psychological readiness of future teachers for intercultural interaction contributes to effective interaction with colleagues in a multicultural environment; broadens their worldview, helps them feel confident in different cultural contexts; and fosters students' respect for other cultures and global thinking skills.

Conclusions. Thus, the psychological readiness for intercultural interaction of a student-teacher of a non-philological specialty is an important condition for successful pedagogical activity in the future, as it ensures a comfortable and productive atmosphere in the educational process.

Therefore, the foreign language professional competence of teachers of non-philological specialities is key to successful interaction in a globalised world, where professional and pedagogical activities often involve cooperation with international colleagues and partners.

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